

Analysis of social relations - New era in the interpretation of European scientists

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ANNOTATION

The article analyzes Machiavelli's opinions about society and its social relations, inequality and unrest, as well as the opinions about this problem in European personal society and the fact that many scholars who lived in all periods of the past took this issue seriously and viewed it as an important factor that would maintain the peace of society and ensure its stable development in the future. done

Key words: society, equality, privileges, inequality, laws, customs.

INTRODUCTION

Niccolò Machiavelli's views on religion within social relations were very sharp. He stated that "the moral values of Christianity cannot be put into practice, because the morals of the church, which believes that the highest happiness is

obedience, contempt for worldliness, turning away from life, makes people weak and weak, and makes them victims of fools.¹" While reading these thoughts of Machiavelli, some people may have come to the conclusion that Machiavelli was against religion, or even a fanatic. However, this is an a priori false conclusion. In fact, Machiavelli's thoughts were not directed at religion itself. Perhaps, it is aimed against the application of religion, or rather, the moral values of Christianity to the life of society, and more precisely, against the establishment of the moral values of Christianity as the basis of all social relations in society². Because at the time of Machiavelli's life, such a system was established in most European countries. That is, the moral values of religion determined the way of activity of all social, political, economic, legal, cultural, and educational spheres of society.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

The law, rule, and discipline of the society were or were formed on the basis of these religious moral values. This is not the fault of the religion, but, as we mentioned above, it is the fault of the clergy who used the religion for their personal interests and misapplied the religion to the life of the society³.

As we quoted Andy Machiavelli, who is still a source of controversy to this day, "the use of all means, however immoral, by a unifying, popularly elected reformist king to build a strong, centralized nation-state is, if the result is desirable,

¹ Салимов Б. Л., Файзиёв С. Ф., Курамбаев Ж. (2022). ЕВРОПА ОЛИМЛАРИНИНГ АСАРЛАРИДА ИНСОН ВА ИЖТИМОЙ МУНОСАБАТЛАРНИНГ ЎЗАРО АЛОҚАДОРЛИГИНИНГ ТАҲЛИЛИ. Журнал комплексного образования и исследований , 1 (6), 44–50.

²Бахриддин Лутфуллаевич Салимов (2022). ЖАМИЯТНИНГ ШАКЛЛАНИШИ ВА ТАКОМИЛЛАШУВИДА БОШҚАРУВ ВА ТАРБИЯ САНЪАТИНИНГ ЎРНИ. Academic research in educational sciences, 3 (11), 359-365.

³ Салимов Б. Л., Файзиёв С. Ф., Курамбаев Ж. (2022). ЕВРОПА ОЛИМЛАРИНИНГ АСАРЛАРИДА ИНСОН ВА ИЖТИМОЙ МУНОСАБАТЛАРНИНГ ЎЗАРО АЛОҚАДОРЛИГИНИНГ ТАҲЛИЛИ. Журнал комплексного образования и исследований , 1 (6), 44–50.

can be justified", that is, in short, let's dwell on the well-known and famous comment "The end justifies the means". Since this comment was raised, many attitudes towards it have been expressed and are being expressed. There are different opinions in this relationship. While some approve of this idea, others oppose it. So what did Machiavelli mean by this statement? In this, Machiavelli meant that the head of the state should use all the means for the development of his country, the peace and well-being of his people, and use all the means for the benefit of the whole nation, even though some of these means are immoral, and they are against some representatives of that nation, as well as against the people of other countries. even if it causes oppression and suffering. Just as there are two sides to a coin, there are both positive and negative sides to Machiavelli's reasoning. The positive side is that the ruler works to ensure the prosperity of his country and the well-being of his people. It is important not to forget that when a country develops, when the head of that country wants it first and is constantly searching for it. It is also important that the head of state loves his people and his country. After all, a ruler who loves his people and his country always thinks about the future of his country and creating a decent life for his countrymen⁴.

Shavkat Mirziyoyev, who is the leader of our country, has unlimited love for Uzbekistan and the people of Uzbekistan. This is clearly proven by the work done and improved by President Shavkat Mirziyoyev during the past term. This situation was evident from the first days when Shavkat Mirziyoev started working to improve social relations. This is the virtual reception of the President of the

⁴ Бахриддин Лутфуллаевич Салимов, Одилбек Дониёр Ўғли Бозорбоев, Хусниддин Равшанбек Раджапбаев (2022). ЖАМИЯТДА ИЖТИМОЙ БАРҚАРОРЛИКНИ ТАЪМИНЛАШГА ОИД ФАЛСАФИЙ ҚАРАШЛАР. Academic research in educational sciences, 3 (11), 286-291.

Republic of Uzbekistan and the establishment of public receptions of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan in districts and regions. The purpose of these reception centers is to provide relief to the people⁵, to hear and solve their problems. It was established that not only virtual and public receptions, but also all other state organizations will accept people's appeals and consider them in a short period of time. The President of the Republic of Azerbaijan announced the slogan "state agencies should be servants of the people" and demanded that everyone follow it. Many other things are being done to create a decent way of life for our people, which cannot be enumerated. All these mean one thing, it means that we are led by a person who loves his people and his country. This should be done with gratitude.

At this point, one should not forget that one should love one's homeland and people, create high-level living conditions for it, and not be at the expense of offending some of one's compatriots and spoiling the interests of other nations and peoples. This is a vivid expression of understanding from the other side, that is, the negative side of Machiavelli's phrase "the end justifies the means". But, Makia Well, with his above reasoning, Zinhar probably did not conclude that this level of cruelty is possible. This is clearly confirmed by his comment "Cruelty can be justified if it is used once, even for the benefit of citizens, but it cannot be justified if it is used continuously to oppress citizens."

René Descartes, who went down in history with his important scientific researches in mathematics, geometry and physics, is one of the thinkers who left an indelible mark on the development of philosophical thoughts with his remarkable

⁵Бахриддин Лутфуллаевич Салимов (2022). ЖАМИЯТНИНГ ШАКЛЛАНИШИ ВА ТАКОМИЛЛАШУВИДА БОШҚАРУВ ВА ТАРБИЯ САНЪАТИНИНГ ЎРНИ. Academic research in educational sciences, 3 (11), 359-365.

philosophical views⁶. "Descartes, who is not indifferent to the processes taking place in society, describes several of his moral procedures. Based on them, he builds his life principles, and among them, he calls obedience to the laws and customs of his country the first rule. It should be noted that this principle of life, which was previously put forward by Descartes, has gained importance in all times, both for citizens and for the state. In particular, it has a great role in ensuring socio-political stability in the life of society. It was also useful for the common people⁷. Because the citizens who obeyed the laws and customs of their country continued their peaceful way of life in the society without being persecuted by the state.

It should be said that non-observance of laws and customs within the framework of current social relations occurs mainly in the second and third cases that we have indicated above. Because today, in most countries of the world, a democratic system has been established and a civil society has been established or is continuing to develop towards this goal. Therefore, their laws are formulated on the basis of international democratic requirements, customs are formed on the basis of harmony of national and universal values. Therefore, we think that it would be appropriate if our contemporaries also follow the example of René Descartes' principle.

The development of social relations is determined by the level of enlightenment, mental-intellectual potential, spiritual-cultural, political-legal literacy of the members of the society. Development experiences of human society

⁶ Салимов Б. Л., Мазбутов Д., Жўраев А. (2022). ИЖТИМОЙ МУНОСАБАТЛАРДА ТЕНГЛИК ВА ТЕНГСИЗЛИК ҚОНУНЛАР ВА УРФ -ОДАТЛАРНИНГ ЎЗARO БОҒЛИҚЛИГИ. Journal of Integrated Education and Research, 1(6), 11–17.

⁷ Бахриддин Лутфуллаевич Салимов, Одилбек Дониёр Ўғли Бозорбоев, Хусниддин Равшанбек Раджапбаев (2022). ЖАМИЯТДА ИЖТИМОЙ БАРҚАРОРЛИКНИ ТАЪМИНЛАШГА ОИД ФАЛСАФИЙ ҚАРАШЛАР. Academic research in educational sciences, 3 (11), 286-291.

have already proved the correctness of this conclusion. This is also confirmed by the opinions of many well-known thinkers in the field of philosophy⁸. For example, Julien Offrede Lametri writes in this regard: "Even if you suffer yourself, spread enlightenment and serve the society." Indeed, enlightenment has a great role and importance in social relations. Because learning and following the laws of social relations is done by spreading enlightenment. Without hesitation, we can include the principle of science and enlightenment among the factors that develop social relations. Basically, science is a part of enlightenment, it is an integral part of it. There are also modern trends in philosophy, such as scientism and anti-scientism, which study the role of science in social relations. To make it more understandable to people, the concepts of science and enlightenment are often used together.

Learning and teaching the essence of social relations is the main task of enlightenment. Because it includes a number of concepts such as knowledge, science, education, skills. Enlightenment means educating the people, mastering all fields of science, achieving technical and digital technology achievements, and using them in real life to increase production efficiency in the national economy and agriculture, in general, in all areas of the economy, and in the end, to bring the country's development to a higher level⁹. You see, how great is the power of enlightenment. Those who were able to correctly assess this power and use it effectively are now among the advanced countries of the world. As an example, let's take the country of Japan that we know. The situation of Japan was not good in 1945-1950.

⁸ Салимов Б. Л., Файзиёв С. Ф., Қурамбаев Ж. (2022). ЕВРОПА ОЛИМПЛАРИНИНГ АСАРЛАРИДА ИНСОН ВА ИЖТИМОЙ МУНОСАБАТЛАРНИНГ ЎЗАРО АЛОҚАДОРЛИГИНИНГ ТАҲЛИЛИ. Журнал комплексного образования и исследований, 1 (6), 44–50.

⁹ Бахриддин Лутфуллаевич Салимов, Одилбек Дониёр Ўғли Бозорбоев, Хусниддин Равшанбек Раджапбаев (2022). ЖАМИЯТДА ИЖТИМОЙ БАРҚАРОРЛИКНИ ТАЪМИНЛАШГА ОИД ФАЛСАФИЙ ҚАРАШЛАР. Academic research in educational sciences, 3 (11), 286-291.

The backwardness of the Japanese state at that time and the hard life of the Japanese people were clearly described in the television series "Oshin" and other artistic and documentary films, which were shown on the TV channels of Uzbekistan. Thirty years later, the people and the state, which were in such a difficult situation, got out of the mire of backwardness and reached a high level of development. "Panasonic", "Sony", "Toyota", "Nissan" and many other Japanese companies and manufacturing enterprises have occupied the world market with their products. As a result of the increase in GDP per capita, the standard of living of the Japanese people naturally increased. The real money income of the population increased and the lifestyle became more comfortable. Such short-term development was recognized by the world community as a "Japanese miracle"¹⁰. At present, everyone knows the secret, that is, the important factors of this Japanese miracle. The most important of them: patriot It is the attention of national importance to the state, joint action towards the goal, the rule of law and, of course, enlightenment. At the same time, in Japan, young people's studies, excellent education and diligent mastering of all subjects were controlled at the state level and all conditions were created for this. This approach has paid off. Representatives of a new generation of young people with knowledge, talent, ability, competence and intellectual potential came out, they created that "Japanese miracle" and delivered high-tech products to the world population¹¹.

CONCLUSION

¹⁰ Salimov B.L. Expression of Dialectic Categories in the Individual's Social Life // openaccessjournals. eu. International Journal of Innovative Analyses and Emerging Technology. Volume: 1, Issue 4, 2021. -P.16-18.

¹¹ Салимов Б. Л., Файзиёв С. Ф., Қурамбаев Ж. (2022). ЕВРОПА ОЛИМПЛАРИНИНГ АСАРЛАРИДА ИНСОН ВА ИЖТИМОЙ МУНОСАБАТЛАРНИНГ ЎЗАРО АЛОҚАДОРЛИГИНИНГ ТАҲЛИЛИ. Журнал комплексного образования и исследований , 1 (6), 44–50.

Then naturally a question arises. Well, if obeying laws and customs is necessary and useful, why doesn't everyone follow this procedure. Who are those who violate the laws of the state, who deny the customs of society? As a correct answer to this question, the following several considerations can be given:

First of all, the laws established in the state are unfair and the established customs are obsolete. Such situations exist in times of slavery, feudalism, and in dictatorships and autocratic regimes based on a single rulership;

secondly, the existence of different approaches to obeying laws and customs. For example, what is impossible for many people is possible for others. Or, in other words, there is punishment for some of those who disobey the laws and customs, and not for others;

thirdly, the laws of the country are fair and the customs are all in order, but the citizens disobey for various reasons, sometimes from immorality, sometimes from legal illiteracy, sometimes from carelessness, sometimes deliberately and for other reasons.

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